

Volume 08 Issue 01
Jan-April 2026

*Corresponding

Author:

Ramesh Krishnan S

Department of

Mechanical Engineering,

Rajiv Gandhi Institute of

Technology (Government

Engineering College),

Kottayam, Kerala, India

Submission Date: Feb
26, 2025

Copyright Received

Date : Feb 27, 2025

Published Date: ***

Numerical Analysis of Heat Transfer Performance of a Battery Pack Hybrid Cooling System Using Cu-Al₂O₃ Hybrid Nanofluid in Aluminium Minichannel and a Phase Change Material

Ramesh Krishnan S, Christo Joseph, Nandana S., Nikhil Sam Punnoose, Noel M Jacob*

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Technology (Government Engineering College), Kottayam, Kerala, India

ABSTRACT

A hybrid thermal management system (HTMS) which integrates both active and passive cooling techniques aims to increase heat dissipation, attain uniform temperature and improve battery life. HTMS for lithium-ion batteries is proposed in this paper integrating phase change material (PCM), Cu-Al₂O₃ hybrid nanofluid (HNF) and aluminum minichannels to enhance heat dissipation and temperature regulation under high discharge conditions. Key variables including operating temperature, flow rate, volume concentration of nanoparticles, and cooling medium used in the minichannel are investigated to assess their impact on thermal performance. In this design, the PCM (paraffin wax) acts as a passive cooling element, absorbing and releasing heat to stabilize temperatures, while the cooling medium in the minichannel provides active cooling enhancing convective heat transfer. The combined effects of PCM and cooling medium on reducing maximum temperatures, improving temperature uniformity and managing energy consumption, particularly in electric vehicles and high-power applications are analyzed. It is concluded that HNF consistently provides the lowest battery temperature than single particle nanofluid and water proving its superior heat dissipation capability. Also, HTMS using HNF and PCM is a highly effective thermal management solution for lithium-ion batteries, suitable for electric vehicles and energy storage systems.

Keywords: *Lithium-ion battery, battery thermal management, hybrid thermal management system, hybrid nanofluid, Phase change material, minichannel, Reynolds number*

Nomenclature

C_p	specific heat capacity J/kg K
D_h	hydraulic diameter m
k	thermal conductivity W/m K
p	pressure Pa
q	heat generation rate per unit volume W/m^3
T	temperature K
u	velocity vector
v	velocity m/s
μ	dynamic viscosity Pa s
ρ	density kg/m^3
ϕ	volume fraction of nanoparticle

Subscripts

bf	base fluid
nf	nanofluid
np	nanoparticle

Acronyms

BTMS	Battery Thermal Management System
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
HNF	Hybrid nanofluid
HTMS	Hybrid Thermal Management Systems
PCM	Phase Change Material

INTRODUCTION

Lithium-ion batteries exhibit peak performance within a temperature range of 15–40°C [1]. Since a typical battery pack consists of multiple cells arranged in series and parallel configurations to meet the required power output, heat accumulation within the pack can lead to localized overheating. The magnitude of heat generation depends on charge/discharge rates, internal resistance of the cell and surrounding environmental conditions. If not managed properly, this localized heating can degrade battery performance, accelerate aging, and in extreme cases, trigger catastrophic failures such as thermal runaway. When the temperature exceeds 60°C, the risk of thermal runaway increases significantly and will lead to battery failure. Thermal runaway is a self-sustaining exothermic reaction that leads to a rapid rise in

temperature, which can eventually result in cell venting, fires, or explosions [2]. The most serious concern reported with lithium-ion battery is that there is considerable reduction in its performance when subjected to inadequate thermal management. High temperatures make them more prone to internal short-circuiting [3]. Thus maintaining the battery temperature within an optimal range is essential for ensuring safety, reliability and efficiency. To prevent these issues, Battery Thermal Management Systems (BTMS) perform a vital role in sustaining optimum operating temperatures. A well-designed BTMS must be capable of functioning efficiently in a variety of environmental conditions while remaining cost effective, compact and lightweight to support the widespread adoption of lithium-ion batteries in electric vehicles as well as other applications.

Active and passive cooling systems are essentially used in the thermal management of battery cells. An active cooling system consumes energy and dissipates energy by forced convection. But in the passive type, no external energy is used but heat transfer is by conduction, convection and radiation. [4]. Air cooling is a simple and cost-effective method using forced air convection to dissipate heat. However, it is inefficient for high-power applications due to low heat transfer coefficients and specific heat value [5,6].

Numerous studies have explored the thermal behavior of lithium-ion batteries and effectiveness of various BTMS solutions. Among them, liquid cooling has received substantial attention due to its higher heat dissipation properties compared to air cooling. Liquid cooling involves the circulation of coolants such as water or dielectric fluids to absorb heat. Though it is more effective than air cooling, it increases system complexity and energy

consumption. Zhao et al. [7] conducted numerical simulations on cylindrical battery cells to analyze their thermal behavior when cooled using minichannel liquid BTMS. Their study examined parameters such as flow rate, channel size, number of cooling channels etc. A notable finding is that increasing the size of the channel entrance at a constant flow rate results in reduced heat dissipation. This result highlights the importance of optimizing cooling channel geometries to maximize heat transfer efficiency. The characteristics of heat transfer of laminar flow nanofluids in a rectangular channel are investigated by Ahmed et al. and conclude that heat transfer coefficients increase with Reynolds number and volume fraction [8]. Another critical aspect of BTMS design is the direction of coolant flow and its influence on both battery temperature and the energy required for fluid circulation. Lan et al. [9] performed numerical simulations on prismatic battery cells cooled by aluminum minichannels. Their study emphasizes the impact of coolant flow direction on battery thermal behavior and shows that flow arrangement plays a key role in determining temperature uniformity and cooling efficiency. The contact interface between cooling channels and battery modules is another important design consideration. The impact of expanding the contact area between the battery module and cooling channels was investigated by Zhao et al. [10]. Their findings show that while a greater contact surface considerably lowers the maximum battery temperature, it also causes the temperature homogeneity throughout the battery pack to decrease.

This highlights a critical trade-off in BTMS design - while increasing contact area enhances heat dissipation, it may also introduce temperature gradients that can impact overall battery performance.

Furthermore, the study emphasizes that at higher discharge rates which also raise the temperature, optimizing coolant flow rate becomes even more crucial for maintaining safe operating temperatures. Design optimization of cooling systems has also been explored by Deng et al. [11], who proposed a new cooling design for lithium-ion batteries. Their research focused on how various geometric and flow parameters, including cooling channel width, length, thickness and mass flow rate influence cooling efficiency. Their findings demonstrate that by fine-tuning these parameters, BTMS performance can be significantly enhanced, leading to better temperature control and improved energy efficiency.

The exclusive properties of nanofluids [12] have made them attractive candidates for various industrial heat transfer applications. Since nanofluids are known for their better heat transfer properties compared to base fluids, their use permits the design for compact, lightweight cooling systems. This is predominantly advantageous in cases where weight and space are crucial elements as in electric vehicles. Novel cooling system utilizing water-based nanofluids are also proposed [13]. Huo et al. [14] conducted numerical studies on the effects of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles on BTMS performance. Their results indicate that incorporating a 4% volume fraction of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles in the coolant reduces maximum battery temperatures by up to 7%, demonstrating the potential of nanofluids in battery cooling. Mondal et al. tried different nano fluids and analyzed their impact on temperature distribution within typical battery modules for two different flow configurations. They confirm the efficacy of nanofluids' effective thermal safety of lithium-ion batteries without performance penalty [15].

Hybrid nanofluids (HNF) are replacing single particle nanofluids in heat transfer

applications because of their superior thermal performance. HNF combines two or more types of nanoparticles in a base fluid to enhance thermal conductivity, heat capacity, and convective heat transfer characteristics. Recent advancements in HNF have introduced new possibilities for improving thermal management in lithium-ion batteries. Nandakishore et al. [16] investigated the performance of straight, wavy, and semi-wavy mini-channel designs using CuO-Al₂O₃ HNF. Their findings revealed that the semi-wavy channel design performed best at lower flow rates, while the wavy design exhibited superior performance at higher flow rates when deionized water is used as the base fluid. Additionally, all tested designs achieved a Performance Enhancement Coefficient (PEC) greater than 1, indicating a net improvement in heat transfer efficiency. An analysis of the thermal and hydraulic characteristics of semi-wavy mini-channels with varying wave amplitudes (0.2–0.6 mm) using water-ethylene glycol-based nanofluids [17] shows that a 0.6 mm wave amplitude with a 1% alumina nanofluid yielded the highest heat transfer efficiency.

In addition to liquid cooling, Phase Change Materials (PCM) have emerged as an effective passive cooling solution due to their high latent heat capacity. PCMs absorb heat during melting and release it during solidification, helping to maintain a stable battery temperature. Sabbah et al. [18] compared forced air cooling and PCM based cooling in extreme environmental conditions. Their findings reveal that while forced air cooling is not so effective in averting thermal runaway, PCM based systems can successfully maintain battery temperatures below critical limits, even under high ambient temperatures. Use of PCM makes temperature to be more uniformly distributed and reduces the surface temperature [19]. Further research by

Lazark et al. [20] investigated how PCMs with different melting points affect thermal performance. Their study indicates that higher melting point PCMs improve overall heat dissipation making them suitable for high-power applications. However, challenges such as limited thermal conductivity of PCMs necessitate further research into hybrid cooling approaches. PCMs exhibit low thermal conductivity (in the range 0.22–0.53 W/mK) which results in poor heat transfer rate. Also, the full energy storage capacity of a system cannot be made use of due to very sluggish heat storage [21]. A summary of research pertaining to the applications of different media such as air, liquid, nanofluids, PCM, heat pipe and combinations of these techniques for battery thermal management is provided by Olabi et al [22]. An overview of the thermal characterization of lithium-ion batteries stressing on the enhancement of their long-term durability and sustainability is given by Chaubey et al [23].

Hybrid Thermal Management Systems (HTMS) where passive cooling system is integrated with an active cooling system that provide superior cooling performance. They provide distinct advantages such as improved uniformity in temperature, reduced energy consumption of cooling systems, extended lifespan of battery, higher adaptability and safe operation. HTMS incorporating micro heat pipe arrays, convective air and intermittent spray water reported reduction in maximum temperature, temperature non-uniformity and energy consumption when compared to systems without water spraying [24]. A combination of PCM, copper foam as porous fins and porous layers and liquid cooling will give a considerable reduction in maximum battery surface temperature and increase in energy density [25]. Hybrid cooling system based on nanofluids for BTMS

reduces the temperature rise and subsequently helps in attaining temperature uniformity in comparison with the single BTMS. Use of nanofluids, instead of water, postpones the onset of PCM transition effectively which consequently leads to a decrease in the rate of temperature rise [26].

This study proposes a HTMS that combines PCM, Cu-Al₂O₃ HNF and aluminum mini-channels to improve thermal performance in lithium-ion

batteries. Key parameters such as nanoparticle concentration, operating temperature, flow rate and HNF volume fraction are analyzed to optimize cooling efficiency.

DESIGN OF BATTERY PACK

The primary objective of the design is to maintain the desired operating temperature for the battery cells, preventing overheating and thermal runaway. A schematic diagram of the battery pack is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram of battery pack.

The system consists of an aluminum-based minichannel structure where Cu-Al₂O₃ hybrid nanofluid is circulated to provide active cooling. The PCM, housed adjacent to the minichannels, acts as a passive cooling medium by absorbing excess heat and undergoing phase change. PCM provides passive thermal regulation, stabilizing battery temperatures by absorbing excess heat, while the HNF in minichannels enhances convective heat transfer for active cooling. The geometric parameters of the system are carefully selected to ensure uniform cooling distribution. The computational model of the battery pack consists of four battery cells, each surrounded by PCM

compartments, with aluminum minichannels through which the nanofluid flows. Meshing is performed employing a structured mesh to ensure accuracy and computational efficiency. A structured mesh as in Figure 2 is used to discretize the computational domain consisting of 1,208,120 elements, as determined by a grid independence study. A series of simulations are conducted with different mesh densities to ensure that the numerical solution remains unchanged beyond a certain mesh refinement level. The key geometric parameters used in the study include: minichannel width: 0.35 mm, PCM layer thickness: 0.6 mm, battery cell thickness: 1.3 mm.

Fig. 2: Mesh elements.

The boundary conditions are defined to closely mimic real-world conditions. A velocity inlet boundary condition is applied at the entrance of the minichannels ensuring a steady supply of cooling fluid at 298 K. The outlet is defined as a pressure outlet, while the minichannel walls and battery terminals are considered insulated to minimize heat loss. This design configuration ensures effective heat dissipation while maintaining energy efficiency.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS

To accurately simulate the heat transfer behavior within the HTMS, the fundamental conservation equations of mass, momentum and energy are applied [27,28].

Continuity Equation (Mass Conservation)

The mass conservation equation ensures that the mass flow rate remains constant across the domain.

$$\nabla \cdot (\rho u) = 0$$

where ρ = density of the fluid, u = velocity vector.

Momentum Equation (Navier-Stokes Equation)

The motion of the nanofluid through the minichannels is governed by the Navier-Stokes equation.

$$\rho (\partial u / \partial t + (u \cdot \nabla) u) = -\nabla p + \mu \nabla^2 u$$

where μ = dynamic viscosity of the fluid, p = pressure, u = velocity vector.

Energy Equation

The heat transfer in the system and how temperature varies in the system are dictated by the energy conservation equation

$$\rho C_p (\partial T/\partial t + u \nabla T) = k \nabla^2 T + q$$

where C_p = specific heat capacity, T = temperature, k = thermal conductivity, q = heat generation rate per unit volume, u = velocity vector.

Nanofluid Property Models

To model the thermal and physical properties of the Cu-Al₂O₃ nanofluid, empirical equations are used [29,30,31].

Density

The density of the nanofluid is calculated using the equation

$$\rho_{nf} = (1 - \phi) \rho_{bf} + \phi \rho_{np}$$

where ρ_{nf} = density of nanofluid, ρ_{bf} = density of base fluid, ρ_{np} = density of nanoparticles and ϕ = volume fraction of nanoparticles.

Specific Heat Capacity

The specific heat of the nanofluid is estimated using the weighted sum formula

$$C_{p,nf} = [(1 - \phi) C_{p,bf} + \phi C_{p,np}] / \rho_{nf}$$

where $C_{p,nf}$ = specific heat of nanofluid, $C_{p,bf}$ = specific heat of base fluid, $C_{p,np}$ = specific heat of nanoparticles.

Thermal Conductivity (Maxwell Model)

The thermal conductivity of the nanofluid is determined using Maxwell's model

$$k_{nf} = k_f [(k_{np} + 2k_{bf} + 2\phi(k_{np} - k_{bf})) / (k_{np} + 2k_{bf} - \phi(k_{np} - k_{bf}))]$$

where k_{nf} = thermal conductivity of nanofluid, k_{bf} = thermal conductivity of base fluid, k_{np} = thermal conductivity of nanoparticles.

Viscosity (Einstein Model)

The viscosity of the nanofluid is estimated using Einstein's equation

$$\mu_{nf} = (1 + 2.5\phi) \mu_{bf}$$

where μ_{nf} = viscosity of nanofluid, μ_{bf} = viscosity of base fluid.

The Reynolds number (Re) determines the nature of fluid flow (laminar or turbulent) and is defined as

$$Re = \rho v D_h / \mu$$

where D_h = hydraulic diameter (m), v = velocity [32].

In this study, the Reynolds numbers considered are 100, 340 and 530, ensuring the flow remained in the laminar regime.

The heat generation within the lithium-ion battery is primarily due to electrochemical reactions and internal resistance. The volumetric heat generation rate used in the study is

$$Vq = -P$$

where $P=3.7W$ (at 4C discharge rate) and V = battery cell volume (m^3). The resulting heat generation rate is approximately $223\text{ kW}/m^3$.

The calculated values of different properties corresponding to different heat transfer media which are used in numerical analysis are tabulated in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1: Properties of different fluids.

Fluid	Density kg/m^3	Thermal conductivity $W/m\ K$	Specific heat $J/kg\ K$	Viscosity $Pa\ s$
Water	998	0.658	4182	0.001
Al ₂ O ₃ 1%	1065	0.725	3650	0.0018
Al ₂ O ₃ 2%	1115	0.78	3350	0.0026
Cu 1%	1120	0.79	3400	0.002
Cu 2%	1175	0.85	3150	0.0029
HNF 1%	1095	0.835	3500	0.0022
HNF 2%	1150	0.895	3250	0.003

Table 2: Velocity of fluids.

Fluid	Velocity for $Re=100\ m/s$	Velocity for $Re=340\ m/s$	Velocity for $Re=530\ m/s$
Water	0.0258	0.0878	0.137
Al ₂ O ₃ 1%	0.0436	0.148	0.23
Al ₂ O ₃ 2%	0.06	0.204	0.319
Cu 1%	0.046	0.156	0.243
Cu 2%	0.064	0.216	0.337
HNF 1%	0.0518	0.176	0.2744
HNF 2%	0.067	0.229	0.356

METHODOLOGY

The methodology involves Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulation using ANSYS Fluent to analyze the thermal performance of the HTMS. The study integrates Cu-Al₂O₃ as HNF and paraffin wax as PCM (which has high chemical

stability, high latent heat, low cost and corrosion resistance) in aluminum minichannels whose properties are defined in ANSYS Fluent (Table 3) [33]. The liquidus and solidus temperatures of PCM are 318K and 315K respectively.

Table 3: Material properties.

Properties	Aluminium	Lithium battery	Paraffin wax – solid	Paraffin wax-liquid
Density	2719	2750	900	770

(kg/m ³)				
C _p (J/kg K)	871	1250	1929	2383
k (W/mK)	202.4	1	0.2	0.2

Cell zone conditions

Battery - Solid - Source term provided to enable heat generation.

PCM – solid/melting - solidification/melting model enabled.

Minichannel - fluid - Velocity inlet and pressure outlet is mentioned, and boundaries are defined as aluminium solid.

Boundary conditions and assumptions

The following boundary conditions are applied:

- **Inlet:** Velocity inlet at 298 K and fluid flow velocity determined by Reynolds number (100, 340, and 530).
- **Outlet:** Pressure outlet with zero-gauge pressure.
- **Minichannel walls:** Insulated (adiabatic condition).
- **Battery terminals:** Insulated to prevent heat dissipation.
- **Heat generation:** Internal heat source of 3.7 W per battery cell.

The following assumptions are also made:

- Exterior surfaces are insulated,

meaning no external heat loss.

- Uniform concentration of nanoparticles in the nanofluid (single-phase approach).
- No radiation heat transfer, as conduction and convection dominate in small-scale systems.
- Uniform heat generation within the battery cells.
- Flow is laminar since the maximum Reynolds number is 530.
- No heat transfer at the battery terminals, ensuring all heat dissipates through the cooling system.

After running the simulations, the temperature contours at different Reynolds numbers are obtained to visualize cooling performance. The effect of different cooling fluids on temperature reduction is compared.

The simulation results are compared with experimental data from literature [32], focusing on battery temperature evolution over time as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Design for validation.

A 4C discharge rate is used in both the simulation and the experimental study with a heat generation rate of 3.7 W per

cell. The comparison is shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4: Graph of analysis model v/s experimental model.

It can be observed that both CFD and experimental curves follow a nearly identical trend. The maximum temperature deviation is only 3.11 K, occurring at 1000s with a percentage error of 1.02%. This minimal discrepancy confirms that the CFD model provides highly accurate predictions of battery cooling behavior. The temperature stabilizes after the initial cooling phase, confirming the effectiveness of PCM and nanofluid integration in maintaining thermal

stability.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION
Effect of Reynolds Number on Cooling Effect

The study examined the effect of different Reynolds numbers ($Re = 100, 340, 530$) on battery temperature regulation. Figure 5 and Figure 6 give a comparison of the temperature generated at two different Re values (100 and 530), the medium of heat transfer in the minichannel being assumed as water.

Fig. 5: Temperature contour at $Re = 100$ with water as medium.

Fig. 6: Temperature contour at $Re = 530$ with water as medium.

Fig. 7: Effect of Reynolds number on the maximum temperature of the pack with water as the medium in the Minichannel.

The maximum temperature drops as the Re value increases. A drop of around 4K can be observed as the Re value increases from 100 to 530 with water as the cooling medium. Identical results are obtained if water is replaced by single particle nanofluid or hybrid nanofluid. The results shown in Figure 7 demonstrate that higher Reynolds numbers improve cooling performance as increased flow velocity enhances convective heat transfer. At $Re = 530$, the battery temperature is the lowest confirming that higher fluid velocity leads to better heat dissipation. The maximum temperature developed initially increases

with a very high slope and it can be seen that the slope suddenly decreases indicating that the melting process of PCM material (paraffin) has begun. After this stage, only a gradual increase in temperature is observed.

Effect of Medium used on Cooling Effect

The cooling efficiency of water, Cu (1% & 2%), Al_2O_3 (1% & 2%) and HNF (1% & 2%) are analyzed. The maximum temperature generated in the battery pack for different coolants and coolant flow rates are tabulated in Table 4. As a particular case, Figure 8, Figure 9 and

Figure 10 show the temperature contour at 3600s at $Re = 530$, when Al_2O_3 - water nanofluid, Cu-water nanofluid and Cu-

Al_2O_3 HNF are respectively the medium used in the minichannel, each of volume fraction 2%.

Fig. 8: Temperature contour at 3600s at $Re = 530$ for Al_2O_3 (2%).

Fig. 9: Temperature contour at 3600s at $Re = 530$ for Cu (2%).

Fig. 10: Temperature contour at 3600s at $Re = 530$ for HNF (2%).

Table 4: Maximum temperature developed for different coolants through Minichannel.

Medium in the minichannel	Maximum temperature (K) for different Re values		
	Re = 100	Re = 340	Re = 530
Al ₂ O ₃ (1%)	322.45	321.83	321.10
Al ₂ O ₃ (2%)	322.18	321.69	320.97
Cu (1%)	324.38	323.24	322.92
Cu (2%)	324.01	322.92	321.95
HNF (1%)	321.69	320.61	319.88
HNF (2%)	319.97	319.12	318.79

Fig. 11: Variation in maximum temperature of battery pack with different cooling media and mass flow rates.

As in the case of water, as the mass flow rate increases, cooling effect also increases on using different media. Clearly, among the different cooling media, HNF provides the maximum cooling effect or reduction in the temperature of the battery pack as

observed from Figure 11.

Figure 12, Figure 13 and Figure 14 respectively show the temperature plots at 3600s for the different fluids and at the Reynold number values considered.

Fig. 12: Temperature distribution at $Re=100$.

Fig. 13: Temperature distribution at $Re=340$.

Fig. 14: Temperature distribution at $Re=530$.

HNF (2%) exhibited the best cooling performance, reducing the battery temperature to the lowest value when compared to other fluids, at $Re = 530$. Al_2O_3 and Cu nanofluids show improved heat transfer over water, but HNF provides the optimal cooling. Higher nanoparticle concentration (2%) results in better cooling due to enhanced thermal conductivity. HNF also exhibits more uniform temperature distribution compared to single component nanofluids minimizing thermal hotspots.

CONCLUSIONS AND INFERENCE

In this paper, an HTMS is proposed to enhance heat dissipation and temperature regulation under high discharge conditions in lithium-ion batteries. The variables taken into account for assessing the thermal performance include operating temperature, flow rate and volume fraction of nanoparticles in the nanofluid within the minichannels so as to assess their impact on thermal performance.

The following conclusions are arrived at from the analysis:

- Higher mass flow rate improves cooling efficiency.
- HNF (2%) consistently provides the lowest battery temperature proving its superior heat dissipation capability.
- HNF outperform single-particle nanofluids (Cu and Al_2O_3) and water in all cases.
- Al_2O_3 based nanofluids perform better than Cu based nanofluids, showing the impact of nanoparticle selection.
- Water is the least effective coolant highlighting the need for advanced cooling fluids in high-performance battery applications.
- The integration of PCM stabilizes temperature fluctuations, preventing thermal runaway risks.
- HTMS using HNF and PCM is a highly effective thermal management solution for lithium-ion batteries, suitable for electric vehicles and energy storage systems.
- Temperature uniformity improves

significantly with HNF, reducing the risk of localized overheating and thermal runaway, ensuring safer battery operation.

- The integration of PCM provides passive cooling, stabilizing temperatures during peak heat generation, while the active cooling from HNF in minichannels enhances convective heat transfer.

The integration of these techniques aims to reduce peak battery temperatures, improve temperature uniformity and optimize energy consumption. By mitigating thermal runaway risks and extending battery life, this HTMS represents a comprehensive solution for next-generation battery thermal management. In addition to electric vehicles, HTMS finds potential applications like consumer electronics (devices such as smartphones, laptops, and tablets require efficient battery cooling systems to prevent overheating and performance degradation), renewable energy storage such as battery storage systems in solar and wind energy applications, aerospace and aviation (space missions), high power robotics, grid level energy storage, industrial power backup systems etc. The successful implementation of HTMS will significantly enhance the performance, safety and reliability of lithium-ion batteries across various applications, paving the way for future advancements in energy storage technologies. Experimental validation and prototype testing will help to assess real-world performance of the HTMS. Optimization of nanoparticle concentration and exploring advanced materials like graphene-based nanofluids for enhanced cooling are also suggested. The system needs to be scaled up for electric vehicles and renewable energy storage integrating it with battery management systems. The long-term durability is also to be ensured for

efficient and sustainable operation.

REFERENCES

1. Chidambaranathan, B., Vijayaram, M., Suriya, V., Sai Ganesh, R., & Soundarraaj, S. (2020). A review on thermal issues in Li-ion battery and recent advancements in battery thermal management system. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 33, 116–128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.03.317>
2. Shahid, S., & Agelin-Chaab, M. (2022). A review of thermal runaway prevention and mitigation strategies for lithium-ion batteries. *Energy Conversion and Management: X*, 16.
3. Srivastava, G., Nandan, R., & Das, M. K. (2022). Thermal runaway management of Li-ion battery using PCM: A parametric study. *Energy Conversion and Management: X*, 16.
4. Nazar, M. W., Iqbal, N., Ali, M., Nazir, H., & Amjad, M. Z. B. (2023). Thermal management of Li-ion battery by using active and passive cooling methods. *Journal of Energy Storage*, 61.
5. Paccha-Herrera, E., Calderón-Muñoz, W. R., Orchard, M., Jaramillo, F., & Medjaher, K. (2020). Thermal modeling approaches for a LiCoO₂ lithium-ion battery: A comparative study with experimental validation. *Batteries*, 6(3), 40.
6. Sharma, A. R., Sai, C. S., Kumar, A., Reddy, R. V. J., Danyharsha, D., & Jilte, R. (2021). Three-dimensional CFD study on heat dissipation in cylindrical lithium-ion battery module. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 46, 10964–10968.
7. Zhao, J., Rao, Z., & Li, Y. (2015). Thermal performance of mini-channel liquid cooled cylinder-based battery thermal management for cylindrical lithium-ion power battery. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 103,

- 157–165.
8. Ahmad, U. K., Hasreen, M., Yahaya, N. A., & Rosnadiyah, B. (2017). Comparative study of heat transfer and friction factor characteristics of nanofluids in rectangular channel. *Procedia Engineering*, *170*, 541–546.
 9. Lan, C., Xu, J., Qiao, Y., & Ma, Y. (2016). Thermal management for high power lithium-ion battery by minichannel aluminum tubes. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, *101*, 284–292.
 10. Zhao, C., Cao, W., Dong, T., & Jiang, F. (2018). Thermal behavior study of discharging/charging cylindrical lithium-ion battery module cooled by channeled liquid flow. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, *120*, 751–762.
 11. Deng, T., Ran, Y., Zhang, G., & Yin, Y. (2019). Novel leaf-like channels for cooling rectangular lithium-ion batteries. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, *150*, 1186–1196.
 12. Kalsi, S., Kumar, S., Kumar, A., Alam, T., & Dobrotă, D. (2023). Thermophysical properties of nanofluids and their potential applications in heat transfer enhancement: A review. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, *16*(11).
 13. Hasan, H. A., Togun, H., Abed, A. M., Mohammed, H. I., & Armaghani, T. (2025). Cooling lithium-ion batteries with silicon dioxide–water nanofluid: CFD analysis. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, *208*.
 14. Huo, Y., & Rao, Z. (2015). Numerical investigation of nanofluid-based cylindrical battery thermal management using lattice Boltzmann method. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, *91*, 374–384.
 15. Mondal, B., Lopez, C. F., & Mukherjee, P. P. (2017). Exploring the efficacy of nanofluids for lithium-ion battery thermal management. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, *112*, 779–794.
 16. Nanda, P. V. R., Venkatachalapathy, S., & Kalidoss, P. (2022). Experimental investigation on thermohydraulic performance of hybrid nanofluids in a novel minichannel heat sink. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4217410>
 17. Kishore, P. V. R. N., Venkatachalapathy, S., & Reddy, V. S. (2024). Experimental and numerical investigation on thermal and hydraulic performance of semiway minichannels using water–ethylene glycol-based nanofluids. *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*, *149*, 9805–9818.
 18. Sabbah, R., Kizilel, R., Selman, J. R., & Al-Hallaj, S. (2008). Active (air-cooled) vs. passive (phase change material) thermal management of high power lithium-ion packs: Limitation of temperature rise and uniformity of temperature distribution. *Journal of Power Sources*, *182*(2), 630–638.
 19. Duan, X., & Naterer, G. F. (2010). Heat transfer in phase change materials for thermal management of electric vehicle battery modules. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, *53*(23–24), 5176–5182.
 20. Lazrak, A., Fourmigué, J. F., & Robin, J. F. (2018). An innovative practical battery thermal management system based on phase change materials: Numerical and experimental investigations. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, *128*, 320–332.
 21. Murali, G., Sravya, G. S. N., Jaya, J., & Naga Vamsi, V. (2021). A review on hybrid thermal management of battery packs and its cooling performance by enhanced PCM. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, *150*.
 22. Olabi, A. G., Maghrabie, H. M., Adhari, O. H. K., Sayed, E. T., Yousef, B. A. A., Salameh, T., Kamil,

- M., & Abdelkareem, M. A. (2022). Battery thermal management systems: Recent progress and challenges. *International Journal of Thermofluids*, 15.
23. Chaubey, V., Kumar, A., Sinha, S., & Verma, R. (2024). An overview on thermal characterization of lithium-ion batteries for enhancing durability. In *Heat transfer enhancement techniques: Thermal performance, optimization and applications*. Wiley.
24. Yue, Q. L., He, C. X., Jiang, H. R., Wu, M. C., & Zhao, T. S. (2021). A hybrid battery thermal management system for electric vehicles under dynamic working conditions. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 164.
25. Keyhani-Asl, A., Perera, N., Lahr, J., & Hasan, R. (2025). Innovative hybrid battery thermal management system incorporating copper foam porous fins and layers with phase change material and liquid cooling. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 268.
26. Kiani, M., Ansari, M., Arshadi, A. A., et al. (2020). Hybrid thermal management of lithium-ion batteries using nanofluid, metal foam, and phase change material: An integrated numerical–experimental approach. *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*, 141, 1703–1715.
27. Koundal, S., Sharma, S. L., & Debarma, A. (2025). Battery thermal management systems for electric vehicles: An overview of cooling techniques and performance optimization. *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*.
28. Yue, Q. L., He, C. X., Wu, M. C., & Zhao, T. S. (2021). Advances in thermal management systems for next-generation power batteries. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 181.
29. Yadav, D., Nirala, A., Kumar, R., & Singh, P. K. (2021). Density variation in nanofluids as a function of concentration and temperature. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 46, 6576–6580.
30. Riehl, R. R., & Mancin, S. (2022). Estimation of thermophysical properties for accurate numerical simulation of nanofluid heat transfer applied to a loop heat pipe. *International Journal of Thermofluids*, 14.
31. Kalsi, S., Kumar, S., Kumar, A., Alam, T., & Dobrotă, D. (2023). Thermophysical properties of nanofluids and their potential applications in heat transfer enhancement: A review. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, 16(11).
32. Tychanicz-Kwiecień, M., & Gil, P. (2024). Experimental investigation of thermal and flow characteristics of a prototype minichannel heat exchanger. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 231.
33. Mashayekhi, M., Houshfar, E., & Ashjaee, M. (2020). Development of hybrid cooling method with PCM and Al₂O₃ nanofluid in aluminium minichannels using heat source model of Li-ion batteries. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 178, 115543.